

Long wavelength distributed feedback tapered quantum cascade lasers

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Abstract: We present a study on distributed feedback tapered quantum cascade lasers emitting at 14 μm . The fabricated lasers with taper angles between 0° and 3° exhibited output powers scaling in accordance with the active zone volume increase. Reduced divergence angles as small as 4.2° have been obtained with diffraction limited-beam quality ($M^2 \approx 1$). With a first order Bragg-grating for single longitudinal mode selection, continuous wave operation was demonstrated up to almost room temperature with side-mode suppression ratios greater than 20 dB.

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1. Introduction

Quantum cascade lasers (QCLs) are a class of lasers obtained by precise engineering of the electronic wavefunctions within the conduction band of an artificial semiconductor. The latter is realized via periodic repetition of material stacks, that behave as quantum wells and barriers [1]. The laser transition takes place between confined states in the conduction band, in a cascaded scheme, such that each electron can emit more than one photon. The energy separation of the intersubband transition can be finely tuned by tailoring the thickness of the wells and the barriers. Since the transition energy is independent from the employed semiconductor, wide spectral ranges can be covered with the same materials.

Since their invention in 1994, QCLs have become the mid-IR source of choice, thanks to their high brilliance, coherence and directionality, which as a whole provide an exciting playground for chemical sensing applications [2]. In the mid-IR region, fundamental roto-vibrational transitions of many chemical compounds take place. The corresponding absorption features are chemically specific, which can be used for highly sensitive and selective spectroscopy, with main areas of application including environmental sensing, industrial process control and health diagnostics.

The thriving research in this field catalyzed the development of quantum cascade laser sources. Nowadays, QCLs have been extensively improved through advanced band engineering, waveguide fabrication and heat extraction capabilities, in almost over the whole mid-IR spectral range. Wall-plug efficiencies as high as 30% at room temperature (RT) in pulsed operation have been recently reported at 4.9 μm [3], and up to 9% in continuous wave (CW) operation at RT for a 7.7 μm QCL [4], with optical peak powers in excess of several watts.

The long-wavelength mid-IR region ($\lambda > 10 \mu\text{m}$) plays a pivotal role for the detection of BTEX compounds (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylene). BTEX are representative of the larger class of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and are used for monitoring air quality in urban areas. They exhibit strong fundamental roto-vibrational absorptions in the long-wavelength region of the mid-IR spectrum (660–800 cm^{-1}). For a long time, this region has been unexplored because of the lack of high performance QCLs due to both fundamental and material limitations. Among the first, the main issues involve the rapid decrease of the upper-state lifetime with the increasing

wavelength and the presence of resonant losses in the core region due to multiphonon absorption [5]. The waveguide design also plays a fundamental role, since free-carrier scattering losses, introduced by material doping, scale as λ^2 [6]. Among the available material systems, InAs/AlSb compounds on InAs substrate provide several advantageous features, namely the small electron effective mass and the good material transparency below 20 μm due to the favorable position of its Reststrahlen band located at lower energies compared with other materials employed in QCLs. Overall, these InAs properties result in a higher gain material and consequently lower threshold current density. Designs optimized at the University of Montpellier and based on InAs system, led to long-wavelength QCLs with threshold current densities as low as 0.6 kA/cm^2 at RT in pulsed operation [7], which outperform lasers based on other material systems. Room-temperature continuous wave operation of InAs-based QCLs at wavelengths up to almost 18 μm has been reported [8].

In many applications, high optical power and good beam quality are pre-requisites for optimal performance in sensing systems especially for indirect detection schemes such as photoacoustic and photothermal spectroscopies [9–15]. The inherent low photon energy of long-wavelength radiation limits the optical power output. Several approaches can be used to improve the output power, while preserving the beam quality. Among them, the MOPA (Master Oscillator Power Amplifier) and the tapered laser, have the benefit of increasing the available active volume of the device, without allowing the oscillation of high order transverse modes. In a MOPA, a laser oscillator is combined with an active tapered waveguide which acts as a single pass amplifier. The laser waveguide is designed such that it only supports the fundamental mode that is consequently amplified in the tapered waveguide. The two sections can be individually pumped to optimize the device properties, at the expense of system complexity. On the other hand, the tapered laser comes as a monolithic device, incorporating the tapered waveguide in the laser cavity. Here, the ridge section behaves as a transversal mode filter, selecting the fundamental mode by introducing high losses for higher order modes. The electric field adiabatically expands in the tapered section, which provides an enhanced active volume compared to a standard ridge laser. Another advantage of the tapered geometry consists in smaller slow-axis divergence, due to the larger facet dimension.

In this work we present an investigation on long-wavelength tapered QCLs emitting at 14 μm , exploring taper angles comprised between 0° and 3° . Tapered lasers with Fabry-Perot resonators were compared in terms of electrical and optical properties. The increase in the emitted optical power was comparable to the scaling of the active volume, provided by the geometry of tapered lasers. A first-order grating was fabricated on top of the laser waveguides, for the single-longitudinal mode operation. Distributed feedback tapered QCLs with a side mode suppression ratio (SMSR) above 20 dB were demonstrated, in pulsed and continuous wave operation. Beam quality factors close to unity have been found from the far-field intensity distributions, and divergence angles as little as 4° were observed.

2. Laser fabrication

In this work we studied InAs/AlSb QCLs with a design similar to that described in [7]. The structure designed to emit at 14 μm contained 45 active stages which were separated from 3- μm -thick InAs cladding layers doped with Si to $7 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ by 3- μm -thick undoped InAs spacers. The wafer was grown by molecular beam epitaxy on an InAs substrate in a RIBER 412 solid source machine equipped with valved cracker cells for the As and Sb using growth rates of 1.0 and 1.5 \AA/s for AlSb and InAs, respectively.

The tapered waveguides were fabricated via contact photolithography, with a hard mask containing linear taper structures with full-taper angles ranging between 0° and 3° . Deep mesa wet etching ($\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4:\text{H}_2\text{O}_2:\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2:1:2) was performed to define 12- μm -wide ridges. Hard-baked photoresist was used as insulation layer, and the top contact was opened again via contact

photolithography. A metallization layer was finally deposited using electron beam evaporation. The metallization layer was composed of Ti/Au/Cr/Au (20/200/30/200 nm) layers. The devices were cleaved in bars 3.6 mm long, with ridge and tapered parts of equal lengths. The laser bars were mounted epi-side down on AlN gold-coated submounts, using In solder.

A part of the wafer was processed into distributed feedback (DFB) lasers with first order gratings with a periodicity of 2070 and 2080 nm. The gratings were formed on the top of the laser ridges by electron beam lithography and inductively coupled plasma (ICP) etching followed by metallization. The gratings were applied to the full surface of the devices.

In Fig. 1(a) DFB-tapered laser bars are shown (A – 0°, B – 1°, C – 2°, D – 3°). Panels (b) and (c) show SEM micrographs of the tapered facets, with a close-up on the 1° device. On top of the waveguide, the patterned grating can be observed. The typical undercut shape of the waveguide comes from the combination of wet etching, and the different etching rate of the material stack, which gives kinks on the front facet geometry. Such shape, nevertheless, demonstrated to be the most performant for ridge lasers. Moreover, curved sidewall were shown to introduce additional losses in the form of plasmonic and reflection losses for high-order modes [16,17], thus favoring the fundamental transverse mode of tapered lasers.

Fig. 1. (a) Cleaved bar of DFB-Tapered QCLs. Letters from A to D, correspond respectively to 0°, 1°, 2° and 3° taper angle. The orange color comes from the grating diffraction. (b) SEM micrograph of the tapered facets (1°, 2° and 3°). (c) Close-up image of the 1° device: in yellow, the metallization layer; in brown, the hard-baked insulation layer; in dark grey, the active zone.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Long-wavelength tapered QCLs: electro-optical characterization

At first, we provide a description of Fabry-Pérot devices. The FP-tapered lasers were mounted in a cryostat (*Janis*, ST-100) and were biased using a voltage generator (*Agilent*, E3634A), gated by a pulse generator (*Quantum Composers*, 9514+ Pulse Generator). A repetition frequency of 12 KHz with a pulse duration of 330 ns was combined with a slow (30 Hz) square wave modulation superimposed via an arbitrary waveform generator (*Agilent*, 33521A), with a total duty cycle of 0.2%. The emitted radiation was collimated into an FTIR (*Bruker*, Vertex 70 v), using a 2-in. aperture off-axis parabolic (OAP) mirror, with 2-in. focal length. The optical power was collected on the spectrometer's DTGS pyrodetector. Optical power calibrations were carried out using a power meter (*Thorlabs*, PM100D equipped with a S401C measuring head). For these measurements, lasers driven at 2% duty cycle were placed in front of the sensor without any optics. The maximum collection efficiency was expected.

In Fig. 2(a) the LIV curves of the FP-tapered QCLs are presented. As expected, a scaling of the optical power output with the taper angle can be observed, as the active volume of the laser is increased. Interestingly, the slope efficiency of the tapered lasers appears to be higher than that of the ridge devices. This comes from the different collection efficiency of the optical setup, discussed later in this section. An improvement in the slope efficiency in tapered lasers above 85% of the rollover current was observed. Such behavior happens with a strong change in

the optical spectrum, suggesting mode-hopping or mode competition with higher order modes. However, this effect was not encountered in DFB-devices (as shown in Fig. 7(c)).

Fig. 2. (a) LIV curve of the FP-tapered lasers in pulsed operation. The optical power output scales with the taper angle, as the active volume is increased. The peak power scale was calibrated for maximum collection efficiency and does not account for the actual system's collection efficiency. (b) Boxplot of the threshold current densities of the FP-tapered lasers. The threshold current density decreases with the taper angle up to 6%. (c) Peak powers of the FP-tapered lasers, normalized to the average peak power of the ridge lasers. In the shaded area, the estimated power enhancement is displayed. In the solid line, the enhancement from a ridge width of 13 μm is shown; lower and upper limits correspond to ± 1 μm ridge, respectively. In dotted line, the collection efficiency is shown.

In Fig. 2(b-c), the threshold current densities and peak powers of five devices per type are analysed. In the boxplot, the horizontal line represents the mean value, the boxes' limits represent the 1st and 3rd quartiles, and whiskers correspond to the min. and max. values of the tested lasers. Threshold current densities for straight lasers around 0.8 kA/cm² at room temperature were found, in consistence with [7], while values down to 0.74 kA/cm² were measured for tapered lasers. Such behavior has been investigated in similar works [16,18–20], and was explained by the improved mode confinement factor resulting in reduced waveguide losses in the tapered part.

As previously discussed, a different collection efficiency is expected as a consequence of the different divergence angle and collection capabilities of the OAP, whose acceptance angle was estimated to be $\alpha = \sin^{-1}(D/2f) = 30^\circ$. The divergence angle of the lasers, in turn, can be estimated from the beam parameter product (BPP) relation [21,22], as:

$$M^2 = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \sigma_0 \sigma_\theta \quad (1)$$

where λ is the wavelength, M^2 the beam quality factor (with $M^2 = 1$ for an ideal diffracted-limited beam) and $\sigma_{0,\theta}$ are the standard deviation of the near-field intensity distribution and angular intensity distribution. In the assumption of a sinusoidal electric field distribution, the near-field distribution can be expressed as $\sigma_0 \approx 0.18w$, being w the front facet width [23,24].

In Fig. 2(c), the peak powers are shown (boxes) and are compared with the expected power enhancement (shaded area), estimated by the active volume increase and the system collection efficiency (dotted line). The latter includes the theoretical divergence angle of the tapered facet (via Eq. (1), using $M^2 = 1$), integrated over the acceptance angle of the OAP mirror. The straight ridge laser features an emission cone comparable to α , such that a collection efficiency of $\sim 45\%$ is expected. Reducing the slow-axis divergence quickly brings the efficiency close to $\sim 70\%$ (plateau of the dotted line). Above this point, the power enhancement mainly comes from the active volume increase. The continuous line depicts the optical power enhancement, as described before, for a ridge width of 13 μm (lower and upper boundaries represent ridge widths of ± 1 μm , respectively). The experimental data are in good agreement with the expected power enhancement, even if a strong variation from device to device was observed. In conclusion, by

neglecting the different collection efficiency, a power enhancement up to 2.8 times (3° taper) was obtained, which agrees well with the active volume enhancement of ~ 3 .

3.2. Anti-reflection and high-reflection coatings

An approach typically used to improve the extracted power consists in the deposition of thin dielectric films on the laser facet which behave as anti-reflection (AR) and high-reflection (HR) coatings. AR coatings are dielectric thin films which are used to reduce the reflectivity of the front facet, allowing photons to be extracted more efficiently. There are several ways to realize an AR coating. The most advanced consist of the repetition of thin layers, which behave as a narrow passband filter over the designed wavelength region. Such an approach exploits destructive interference of the reflected light, allowing its full transmission. A simplification of this technology is the single quarter-wavelength coating, where a single layer of a dielectric material of thickness $\lambda_n/4$ is used, λ_n being the wavelength in the medium. The optimal transmittance is obtained for a layer's refractive index $n = \sqrt{n_0 n_{eff}}$, n_0 being the air refractive index and n_{eff} the mode effective refractive index in the laser waveguide. For silica (SiO_2) at $\lambda_0 = 14 \mu\text{m}$, a refractive index of 1.783 is found in literature [25], which matches closely with the optimal value of ~ 1.81 . A SiO_2 layer of 1960nm was deposited via sputtering on the front facet of two tapered lasers. It is worth noticing that the larger tapered facet supports a fundamental mode with a higher effective refractive index. Hence, the optimal coating refractive index also increases, leading to a worse performance of the AR-coating if we assume the same deposition thickness. We estimated such variation to be less than 100 ppm in reflectivity (or 0.01% reflectivity change), which justifies our choice of depositing the same layer for all devices.

Application of combined AR/HR coatings allows for further improvement of the slope efficiency and, moreover, for reduction of the threshold current density of only AR-coated devices. Metal deposited on the laser facet are often used as HR coating. To prevent electrical shorting of the device an insulator layer is usually deposited on the facet before its metallisation. In order to verify the suitability of conventional SiO_2/Au coatings at such long wavelengths we performed simulations via the transfer matrix method, presented in Fig. 3. The obtained results might be an over-estimation of the real reflectivity, since diffraction losses are not taken into account.

Fig. 3. Simulated reflectivity for the HR coating, composed by the waveguide material, a SiO_2 layer of variable thickness and a gold layer. The simulation relied on the transfer matrix approach. Refractive indexes for silica and gold were taken from [25].

Following the simulation results we employed a bilayer consisting of 220 nm of SiO_2 and 200 nm of gold deposited on the straight part ridge facets as HR-coating in our devices, sufficiently larger than the penetration depth estimated to be around 17 nm. The LI-curves of the uncoated (as in Fig. 2(a)), AR-coated and AR/HR-coated tapered lasers are shown in Fig. 4, using the same pulsed operation settings (330 ns, 12 kHz repetition rate combined with 30 Hz square wave modulation). After AR-coating, the optical power of the lasers significantly increased and the

HR coating further improved the slope efficiency dP/dI of the devices. The characteristics of the lasers including threshold current densities are summarized in Table 1. After AR-coating, the threshold current density increased by about 18% for both devices as an effect of the higher front mirror losses. The HR-coating decreases J_{th} almost to the values of uncoated devices due to the reduced loss of the back mirror.

Fig. 4. LI-curves of the uncoated (continuous line), AR- (dashed line) and AR/HR-coated (dotted line) tapered lasers operated in pulsed mode.

Table 1. Measured quantities for 1° and 3° taper, before and after coating deposition. Threshold current density, slope efficiency and maximum optical powers are compared. Values in square brackets correspond to enhancement factor compared to the uncoated device.

Device	Quantity	Uncoated	AR	AR/HR
1° Taper	J_{th} (kA/cm ²)	0.738	0.865	0.790
	dP/dI , (mW /A)	66 [1]	171 [2.6]	193 [2.9]
	Max. optical power (mW)	48 [1]	163 [3.4]	201 [4.2]
3° Taper	J_{th} (kA/cm ²)	0.745	0.877	0.772
	dP/dI , (mW /A)	66 [1]	143 [2.2]	165 [2.5]
	Max. optical power (mW)	87 [1]	213 [2.45]	391 [4.5]

The effect of the coatings was analysed using the standard equation for the QCL threshold current density J_{th} including the transparency current J_{tr} [26]:

$$J_{th} = J_{tr} + \frac{(\alpha_w + \alpha_m)}{\Gamma g} = J_{tr} + \frac{\alpha_w}{\Gamma g} - \frac{\ln(R_F R_B)}{\Gamma g} \frac{1}{2L} \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha_m = -\ln(R_F R_B)/2L$ is the mirror loss, α_w is the waveguide loss, Γ is the optical confinement factor, R_F and R_B are reflectivities of the front and back facets, respectively, g is the differential gain and L is the laser length. Reflectivity of uncoated facets can be calculated to be 0.29 from the Fresnel equation.

The transparency current accounts mainly for thermal population of the bottom lasing level, which requires additional electron injection to compensate this effect and to preserve the population inversion. In long wavelength QCLs, J_{tr} is the main component of the threshold current [7].

Any change in the facet reflectivity providing a new value of the mirror loss α_{mc} results in a corresponding change in the threshold ΔJ_{th} that can be negative if the reflectivities R_{FC} and/or

R_{BC} increase:

$$\Delta J_{th} = \frac{\alpha_{mc} - \alpha_m}{\Gamma g} \frac{1}{2L} = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{R_F R_B}{R_{FC} R_{BC}}\right)}{\Gamma g} \frac{1}{2L} \quad (3)$$

Let us first consider the effect of only an AR coating. In the tested lasers the AR-coating resulted in a threshold increase of 0.126 and 0.132 kA/cm² for the 1°- and 3°- tapered laser, respectively. Using a value of modal gain $g = 23$ cm/kA for a similar QCL structure from [7] in Eq. (3) we obtain $\Delta J_{th} = 0.126$ kA/cm² for the reflectivity of AR-coated facet $R_{FC} = 0.035$.

The facet reflectivity can also be found from the slope efficiency of the AR-coated lasers. The portion of generated photons that can escape the laser cavity is defined by the external quantum efficiency:

$$\eta_{ext} = \frac{\alpha_m}{\alpha_m + \alpha_w} \quad (4)$$

In the case of perfect HR coatings on both facets no photon can leave the laser cavity. Inversely, AR coatings improve the light extraction efficiency at the expense of a higher laser threshold produced by the additional loss of photons in the resonator. It is worth noting that in long wavelength QCLs, the threshold increase provoked by the AR coating is less dramatic than at shorter wavelengths. This is mainly due to the high contribution of J_{tr} , which reduces the effect of mirror losses on the threshold current density. Powers of light that leave the resonator through the front (P_F) and back (P_B) facet are related to the facet reflectivities by [27]:

$$\frac{P_F}{P_B} = \sqrt{\frac{R_B(1-R_F)}{R_F(1-R_B)}} = \beta \quad (5)$$

Finally, the slope efficiency of the emission through the front facet dP_F/dI , which is related to the reflectivity of both facets, R_F and R_B , can be expressed as

$$\frac{dP_F}{dI} = \frac{h\nu}{e} \eta_i \frac{P_F}{P_B + P_F} \eta_{ext} = \frac{h\nu}{e} \eta_i \frac{\beta}{(1+\beta)} \frac{\alpha_m}{\alpha_m + \alpha_w} \quad (6)$$

where $h\nu$ is the photon energy, e is the elementary charge, and η_i is the internal differential efficiency [28]. The last equation gives us a possibility to calculate a ratio of the slope efficiencies of the lasers with different treatment of the facets. In these calculations, waveguide losses $\alpha_w \approx 3.6$ cm⁻¹ were used, obtained from a previous study of similar straight devices [7]. We compared the initial slope efficiency of the lasers measured from the tapered side just above the threshold (Table 1) to avoid the influence of mode competition that can affect the expected linearity of the light-current characteristics. Due to the AR-coatings the slope efficiency of the tested devices increased by 2.6 and 2.2 times for 1°- and 3°-tapered lasers, respectively. The reflectivity value of 0.035 obtained from the analysis of the threshold current should result in a smaller increase of 2.1. The observed improvement of the slope efficiency can be achieved if the reflectivity of the AR-coating is in the range 0.01-0.02. On the other hand, with such reflectivity value the threshold current density of the AR-coated QCLs should increase by 0.20-0.16 kA/cm², which is considerably larger than the observed shift. It is worth noting that the maximum optical power of the lasers increased even stronger than the initial slope efficiency by a factor of 3.4 for the 1°-tapered device.

Application of the HR-coating on the back facets of the AR-coated devices increased the slope efficiency by about 12% whereas the threshold current density decreased almost to the characteristics of the uncoated devices with a shift of 0.052 and 0.027 kA/cm² for 1°- and 3°-tapered QCLs, respectively.

The calculated change in the laser characteristics produced by facet coatings is presented in Fig. 5 as a function of the front facet reflectivity for uncoated ($R_B = 0.29$) and HR-coated back facets ($R_B = 0.8$ and 0.99). It is interesting to note that HR-coating has no effect on the slope

efficiency when the reflectivity of the front facet is low, less than 0.01, because all photons leave the laser cavity through its transparent end and their portion reflecting from the back facet is small. Even for the front facet reflectivities of a few percent both the slope efficiency and the threshold current almost do not change when $R_B > 0.8$. The observed J_{th} shifts of the AR/HR-coated lasers are in fair agreement with the calculated data for a front facet reflectivity of about 0.04 and $R_B > 0.9$.

Fig. 5. Calculated increase in the slope efficiency and threshold current density of coated QCLs as a function of the front facet reflectivity for different values of the back facet reflectivity R_B . The uncoated device is taken as reference (zero threshold current increase and slope efficiency increase of 1).

Summarizing the obtained results on AR/HR coating of the tapered QCLs, we should first note the significant increase in the slope efficiency, up to a factor of 2.9 in 1° -tapered lasers, compared with the same uncoated devices. Such improvement can only be obtained when the reflectivity of the front facet is very low, less than 0.01. On the other hand, the observed shifts of the J_{th} after AR and AR/HR coatings correspond to poorer R_F values on the order of 0.04. We consider these data to be more consistent as the threshold current is quite reliably measured whereas the slope of the light-current curves can be affected by the spatial mode competition and the collection efficiency of the optical setup. Otherwise, we should admit that the employed approaches are not valid and should be revised to obtain the expected agreement between the R_F values obtained by the used methods. For instance, the equations here proposed are valid in the assumption of uniform gain and losses within the length of the cavity [29], which might not be true for complex resonators such as the tapered waveguide. In support of this supposition, we should also note that the increase in the total emitted power in the AR/HR-coated devices is even larger than the improvement in the initial slope efficiency in comparison with uncoated lasers, reaching a factor of 4 in the 1° -tapered QCLs.

The studied lasers outperform long-wavelength InAs-based QCLs reported to date, setting a record optical power performance. In addition, the deposition of an AR coating causes only a slight increase in the threshold current density, which is dominated by the transparency current density. The optical power is enhanced by at least 2 times with an AR-coating and up to 4 times with AR/HR coating. It should however be noted that the internal quantum efficiency η_i extracted from the measured slope efficiencies using Eq. (6) is quite low, about 0.07 per stage of the active zone. Improvements of the QCL design are unequivocally required to further increase output power of the devices.

3.3. Far-field measurement

The far-field angular distributions of the tapered lasers were measured by mounting the laser on top of a rotation stage (*Thorlabs*, PRMTZ8), aligning its front facet to the rotation axis. The same driving scheme as the one presented in section 3.1 was applied. The diverging cone of light was collected on a pyrodetector (*InfraTec*, LIE-332f-#) without interposing any optical element between the laser and the detector element. The pyrodetector featured an active element of 1.3 mm diameter and was placed several centimeters apart from the laser facet. The pyrodetector signal was demodulated via lock-in amplifier (*AMETEK*, SR7270) and the magnitude was recorded on a personal computer. Filter order and time constant of the lock-in amplifier were adjusted according to the rotation stage speed, in order to optimize the signal-to-noise ratio while keeping the experiment duration reasonably low.

In Fig. 6(c-f), the intensity distributions for the four laser types are shown. Tapered lasers exhibited narrower far-field distributions in the slow-axis direction, as expected from diffraction theory. The spatial-frequency components of a beam propagating along the z -direction can be obtained, under the paraxial approximation, as:

$$P(s) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} E(x) e^{i2\pi s x} dx \quad (7)$$

being s the spatial frequency ($2\pi s = k_x = (2\pi/\lambda) \sin \theta$), and $E(x)$ the electric field distribution along the slow-axis of the laser facet. The theoretical far-field distributions were calculated from the near-field electric field distributions, obtained via COMSOL simulations. In Fig. 6(a) the electric field distribution of the fundamental TM mode in a 14 μm wide waveguide is presented. Analogous simulations were performed for tapered facets, using ridge widths of 45 μm , 70 μm and 108 μm , according to the laser geometry. The electric field distribution along the slow-axis direction was obtained from the simulation (an example is given in Fig. 6(b)) and used in Eq. (7) to simulate the far-field intensity profile (dots in panels (c-f)), retrieved as the modulus squared of the spatial-frequency distribution. Overall, an excellent agreement between the expected and the experimental far-fields was found, proving that nearly ideal Gaussian beam qualities were achieved along the slow-axis.

Fig. 6. (a) Simulation of a ridge waveguide of 14 μm . The electric field's magnitude for the fundamental TM mode is shown. In red, a cutline passing through the center of the active zone. (b) Electric field's amplitude along the cutline, used to simulate the far-field intensity presented in (c). (c-f) Far-field angular intensity distribution measured for the four lasers (continuous lines). Overlaid in dots, simulation of the expected far-field for the respective laser. In panel (f), an inset of a side-lobe appearance is shown: in light blue, a far-field measurement at higher bias current ($1.8I_{\text{th}}$) is presented. The side-lobe is more pronounced, causing a degradation of the M^2 factor, as shown in Table 2. Aside from the side-lobe, no difference with the low bias current measurement was observed.

The beam quality was estimated from the experimental data, using the second order momentum (standard deviation) of the angular intensity distribution, defined as

$$\sigma_{\theta}^2 = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (\theta - \bar{\theta})^2 I(\theta) d\theta}{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} I(\theta) d\theta} \quad (8)$$

being $\bar{\theta}$ the first order momentum (mean) of the distribution. The Gaussian distribution is the probability density distribution with the smallest standard deviation. Thus, any deviation from Gaussian shape, leads to a deviation from 1 of the beam quality factor. By combining Eqs. (1) & (8), the beam quality factor can be estimated. The standard deviation of the spatial intensity distribution was approximated from the facet width w using the formula $\sigma_0 = 0.18w$. Calculation from the simulated electric field distribution led to similar results. The divergence angle and the beam quality factor for the profiles shown in Fig. 6 are presented in Table 2. Both were estimated for low ($1.5I_{th}$) and high bias current ($1.8I_{th}$), reported in Table 2 to the left and right of the arrow, respectively. A degradation of the beam quality was observed at higher currents, as a consequence of side lobes appearance. An example is shown on the left-wing of the intensity distribution of the 3° taper (inset of Fig. 6(f)).

Table 2. Standard deviation of the angular intensity distribution (σ_{θ}) and beam quality factor (M^2) for the four types of lasers. The values to the left/right of the arrow correspond to low/high current bias, respectively. If a single value is displayed, identical results were found. The M^2 is calculated according to Eq. (1).

Taper angle	σ_{θ}	M^2
0°	26°	$\sim 1^a$
1°	8.03°	1.02
2°	$5.06^\circ \rightarrow 5.13^\circ$	$1.07 \rightarrow 1.08$
3°	$4.23^\circ \rightarrow 4.80^\circ$	$1.29 \rightarrow 1.46$

^aThe quality factor for a narrow ridge suffers from larger near-field distribution errors. This can lead to unphysical values $M^2 < 1$.

3.4. Single longitudinal mode operation

To achieve single frequency operation distributed-feedback (DFB) QCLs were fabricated. A diffraction grating was etched on the top of the laser ridges, in the upper cladding layer of the structure. The grating was then metallized thus forming a metallodielectric periodic structure [30–32]. The relationship between the grating period (Λ) and the Bragg wavelength (λ_B), at which the coherent coupling between the counterpropagating waves occurs, is governed by the Bragg condition [33]:

$$\lambda_B = \frac{2\Lambda n_{eff}}{m}$$

where n_{eff} is the effective refractive index of the waveguide and m is an integer denoting the order of the grating. The metallodielectric waveguide supports two modes satisfying the Bragg condition with different n_{eff} : the semiconductor mode confined under non-etched areas and the metal mode below metallized grating grooves. The semiconductor mode is very similar to the optical mode existing in the QCL waveguide without any grating and its loss does not depend much on the grating geometry. The metal mode with higher loss exhibits anticrossing behavior as a function of the grating depth due to the surface plasmon resonances generated at the metal-dielectric boundary. COMSOL simulations were carried out to find the grating

depth providing an optimal coupling of the DFB modes with the laser waveguide and sufficient difference in their loss to favor single frequency operation. From the simulated periodic structure, a coupling coefficient of $\kappa \approx 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was obtained, with a loss contrast between plasmonic and semiconductor mode of 2 cm^{-1} .

Diffraction gratings with periodicities Λ of 2070 and 2080nm were fabricated for all the four devices, along the full extension of the laser. The lasers were characterized in pulsed operation, with a pulse duration of 100 ns to limit intra-pulse heating effects. The light was collimated into an FTIR (*Bruker*, Vertex 70 v) to record the emission spectra, with a resolution of 0.2 cm^{-1} . The lasers were tested both near the threshold and close to the rollover current, to ensure single mode operation in the whole current range. Emission spectra of the DFB devices are presented in Fig. 7(a): all the tapered lasers exhibited single-frequency emission with a side-mode suppression ratio (shown in the inset with log-scale) greater than 20 dB. A peak wavelength of $\lambda \approx 13.89 \mu\text{m}$ was obtained for all the devices, which from the Bragg condition corresponds to an effective index $n_{\text{eff}} \approx 3.339$, in good agreement with the cross-section waveguide simulations (compare with Fig. 6(a)). In Fig. 7(b), a 1° tapered laser was tested in pulsed operation and tuned across a temperature range between 120 K and 280 K. Emission spectra were collected for bias currents between 300 and 900 mA for each temperature, while no prominent change in the spectrum was observed. For clarity, only the highest current measurement has been kept in Fig. 7(b). The performed analysis suggests mode-hop free tunability in the whole range. In panel (c), the respective LIV curves are portrayed. DFB lasers with shorted 3-mm-long resonators were tested in the CW-regime. The tunability of a 2° DFB-tapered laser is shown in Fig. 7(d). Single-frequency operation (SMSR > 20 dB) was observed between 240 K up to 283 K, where Peltier cooling is readily available. For these devices, optical powers up to 4 mW were achieved in CW-operation without coating deposition. Furthermore, optimization of the coupling coefficient is fundamental to enhance the outcoupled power.

Fig. 7. (a) FTIR spectra of the DFB-tapered lasers collected at room temperature, compared to the spectrum of a Fabry-Perot device. In the insets, the intensities are shown in logarithmic scale. (b) Temperature tuning of a 1° DFB-tapered laser, operated in pulsed mode between 120 K and 280 K and (c) corresponding LIV curves. In panel (b), only the spectra for the highest current of each temperature has been kept. (d) Spectral tuning of a 2° DFB-tapered laser, operated in CW up to 283 K.

The tailoring of the grating periodicity, in combination with temperature and current tuning of the laser would allow targeting benzene or toluene, which exhibit strong absorption bands at 674 cm^{-1} and 694 cm^{-1} , respectively. The single-longitudinal mode operation, combined with the increased optical power and the excellent beam-quality of the tapered lasers, represents a good improvement for the realization of high-performance spectrometers for BTEX detection.

4. Conclusions and further perspectives

Quantum cascade lasers are an attractive solution for the development of MIR sensing platforms. High performance long-wavelength QCLs have been demonstrated in the InAs-AISb material system exploiting the high material gain provided by the small electron effective mass in InAs.

In this work, we explored the tapered laser configuration to improve power outputs, without degrading beam quality. We demonstrated the first long-wavelength tapered lasers, operated above 10 μm . The lasers were able to operate in continuous wave close to room temperature and featured a Bragg grating for single longitudinal mode operation. The tapered geometry improved the output power, as a consequence of the larger active volume, up to a factor of 2.8, which was further enhanced through the deposition of facet coatings. The AR-coating deposition proved to be beneficial, especially in the case of these LW-QCLs, where the high transparency current moderates the effect of increased mirror loss on the threshold current density.

A narrowing of the slow-axis divergence angle was observed and quantified, demonstrating a diffraction-limited beam quality ($M^2 \approx 1$) with the slow axis divergence angles as low as 4.2° . A degradation of the beam quality was observed only for the largest taper angle, under strong current injection.

For future work, optimization of the coupling coefficient and coating deposition will be fundamental to achieve good peak powers in DFB-devices. The improved optical power, together with single mode operation and reduced divergence, will play a pivotal role for the development of high-performance laser-based spectrometers in the long-wavelength infrared.

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Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper can be obtained from the authors upon request.

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